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'This place cannot be tidied up!' Stigmatisation, rats, and place-making in a multispecies city

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a multidisciplinary research project which invited young people to critically re-estimate what is environment and nature, and for whom, in the urbanising world. We describe a series of ethnographic walks aimed at enhancing multispecies arts of attentiveness within the neighbourhood surrounding the participating young people's school, which had a reputation of being disadvantaged. The ethnographic walks focused specifically on mapping human–rat cohabitation in the city. The analysis follows rats, folding empirical accounts from the walks with eclectic disciplinary perspectives. It highlights multispecies childhoods across historical times; environmental educational discourses on purity of nature; waste ontologies; spatial stigma and marginalisation; rats' bodily capacities; and transcorporeal flows of nutrients and dirt. Rather than detecting or visibilising rats' presence in the neighbourhood, we take the hidden presence of rat bodies in the city as provocations to think beyond simple absence or presence in relation to more than human citizenship and spatial stigmatisation. Urban stigmatisation and marginalisation are multispecies processes that emerge with place-making and have consequences for all the multispecies cohabitants of the city. We conclude by offering hesitations concerning the arts of attentiveness, especially when applied in heavily human-dominated circumstances, such as cities, or research.

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In the ongoing 'animal turn' (Rautio, Tammi, and Hohti 2021; Weil 2010; Wolfe 2011), cultural and societal processes previously thought to belong to the sphere of human activity are being resituated within more-than-human relations. The understanding is that all living beings emerge from and make their lives within multispecies communities (Van Dooren, Kirksey, and Münster 2016), and that all seemingly human achievements have in fact been possible thanks to relationships based on support, collaboration, or exploitation humans have with other than human species. Likewise, the consequences of all cultural and societal processes traditionally discussed and theorised in human terms alone fall in the nonhuman animal world as much – or even more – as they fall on us humans.

This article examines urban stigmatisation and belonging as examples of societal phenomena which can be rethought as multispecies. Drawing on childhood geographies, urban studies and

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multispecies studies (e.g. Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006; Horton and Kraftl 2018; Rautio, Tammi, and Hohti 2021) as well as urban anthropological and ecological research, we analyse in detail how these processes are constituted together with particular places such as a school and its surrounding neighbourhood, a shopping mall, materials such as waste and dirt, as well as the bodies of human and nonhuman animals. Furthermore, we zoom out from the ethnographic detail to connect with environmental complexities and challenges on a broader scale, such as those related to urbanisation and the concomitant pollution and biodiversity loss. In thinking about sustainable futures for all inhabitants of a city, we are particularly interested in examining how young people are involved and how their awkward and ambivalent experiences in cities could be taken seriously as environmental relationships (see also Pacini-Ketchabaw and Nxumalo 2016; Rautio et al. 2020). What is the 'nature' of children's everyday environments, and how does this nature come to matter in areas with problematic reputation and stigmas, cohabitated by unloved animals such as rats?

This ethnographic study was conducted in an urban neighbourhood called Bear Hill (pseudonym), commonly associated with marginalisation of its residents in Helsinki, Finland. The interdisciplinary research team, consisting of educational scholars, ecologists, a sociologist, and an anthropologist, worked with secondary school students aiming to practice *multispecies attentiveness* (Van Dooren, Kirksey, and Münster 2016) in order to understand this area as a place inhabited by a range of species beyond the exclusive human perspective. Even if the focus of this paper is this empirical understanding, we also fold in methodological questions, because in multispecies research on urbanity (Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006; Van Dooren, Kirksey, and Münster 2016), which is only emerging, methodological reflection is a necessary part of the process. We describe how the research proceeded through multispecies ethnographic walks mapping the school neighbourhood in terms of human-rat cohabitation. We analyse selected empirical events discussing materials, bodies, stories, sensory elements as well as affects, highlighting these from both different disciplinary perspectives as well as a relational multispecies ontology point of view. Finally, we offer some methodological reflections suggesting ethics of hesitancy concerning arts of multispecies attentiveness (Van Dooren, Kirksey, and Münster 2016).

Places with reputation: stigma and place-making

Recent urban anthropological studies have opened up perspectives into territorial stigma as context-specific processes that often escape classic theories of stigmatisation. Specific places gain a reputation through connections to spatially and historically ordered senses of sociality (Green 2012; Tuominen 2020), whereby the manifold processes of stigmatisation involve layers of affect, stories, histories, and memories. Stigmas are affectively 'sticky' in that they attach specific affects to specific places and materials in ways resistant to change (Ahmed 2014). However, stigmatisation involves tensions between essentialised categories and lived realities and always remains an open process to some extent.

Responses to territorial stigma are often considered in terms of resistance. For example, McBride (2024) showed how an arts project allowed young people living in areas with high levels of poverty to construct alternative narratives and, in this way, gain agency and resist place-based stigma. Here, stigma could be viewed as a 'local resource to do things with' as opposed to just a 'label'. In Halliday and colleagues' study (2021), resistance to spatial stigma could be achieved through (re)claiming public spaces: residents making themselves visible rather than retreating into a private space. Tuominen (2022) emphasises ambivalence in relation to the ways in which residents of a stigmatised area respond to narratives that circulate in the community and media. These responses can reflect struggles for a coherent narrative or a 'moral career' (Goffman 1963); however, at certain moments stigma can lead to pride and a powerful sense of community (Tuominen 2022). According to recent studies conducted in Finnish schools on their partly hidden inequalities. Schools also carry stigmas which are 'sticky' in that they are hard to resist and change and relate to the histories of residential areas in local and affective ways (Bernelius, Huilla, and Lobato 2021). In line with the

anthropologists' views presented above, Peltola and colleagues (2023) argue that there is no straightforward model regarding how stigma is experienced, whereby young people tend to develop positive feelings towards their own school despite stigma.

To make sense of the processes of stigmatisation in more-than-human cities, rather than focusing on agentic individuals or groups of individuals located in a physical neighbourhood responding to an abstract stigma, we turn to the relational notion of place-making (Cresswell 2014; Pink 2008) – that is, processes through which urban places *become* societal and natural ecologies. Place-making as a concept has existed for some time and is marked by openness and change rather than boundedness and permanence (Cresswell 2014). This concept allows the examination of the dynamic collaboration between diverse agencies that produce a place (Pink 2008; Pyry 2016) and helps us to approach the spatiality of the politics of marginalisation and belonging (Spruce 2020). Recently, place-making has been seen as a promising notion when considering the possibilities for multispecies flourishing in urban futures. For example, Houston and colleagues (2018) use place-making as an idea to challenge the ontological exceptionalism of humans in urban planning, and to pay attention to multispecies life and voices.

Through place-making, the city becomes seen as a dynamic, complex, and messy network, 'loosely bound by (local) histories, politics, and cultures as well as by (global) mobilities, flows, and uneasy alliances' (Duhn 2017, 46). This open-ended notion acknowledges the complicated and multilayered character of urban ecologies, which come into view as 'complex assemblages, mutually affecting and affected by their fields of becoming' (Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006, 128). Cities and the phenomena of marginalisation and stigmatisation situated in the urban can also be seen as urban in multiple, manifold ways: that is, 'in more ways than the familiar image of a set of obstacles or opportunities contrived by human technologies and human presence' (Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006, 108).

Our research has been influenced by Hinchliffe and Whatmore's (2006) work on urban place as an entanglement, as well as the idea of multispecies attentiveness as a sensitivity that entails crafting a meaningful response (Van Dooren, Kirksey, and Münster 2016). The formulation of a just response to the matters of co-living in the city is, however, a methodological as well as representational challenge tied to the anthropocentric underpinnings of research, urban planning, and environmental education. The matters of cohabitation are, to follow Hinchliffe and Whatmore (2006), 'matters of controversy' (see also Latour 2004), which cannot be solved based on mere expansion of existing humanist frameworks, rather, these frameworks need to be reworked according to ontological diversity, relational complexity, and the incommensurable forms of communication and desire across species (Chao and Celermajor 2023).

In what follows, we contribute to this reworking by engaging with what can be seen an emerging interest in children's geographies, namely multispecies relationalities on the one hand, and societal divisions, marginalisations and political processes in the lives of children and young people, on the other. Within this strand of work, for example Pacini-Ketchabaw and Nxumalo (2016) and Nelson and Drew (2024) have called for an awareness of histories and ongoing socio-political forces at play in children's multispecies relations. This study's specific contribution lies in our multidisciplinary approach, in which social scientific questions of stigmatisation are weaved in with the material, affective and narrative multispecies ethnographic detail in the field, and young people's local expertise is engaged to theorise rat-human cohabitation as part of more than human place-making. We thus seek to account for multispecies place-making and stigmatisation as intertwined processes that inherently reconceptualise the ways in which we can think about urban co-habitation and belonging. Finally, we reflect on some challenges we met during our research and based on them highlight an ethics of hesitancy as a necessary dimension of multispecies research in the city.

Mapping a multispecies city: ethnographic walks

This study is part of a three-year-long research project which combined education, natural sciences, anthropology, and speculative fiction to develop attentiveness towards multispecies co-habitation in

cities. We engaged groups of young people studying at the secondary school level (ages 13–15) in a process of tracing, mapping, and imagining multispecies city whilst rethinking exclusive human agency and interest. We considered young people as local experts whose insights and observations are invaluable for reshaping environmental thought to encompass cities as nature and as environments for all the species, not only human. During the first, ‘tracing’ phase, we applied a citizen science approach and invited students from three secondary school classes to work with natural scientists to trace rats in their urban communities (see Kervinen et al. 2024). This part of the study included actual tracing using a scientific method and specific track plates – 20 × 20 cm white plastic plates that were painted with lampblack and placed in the neighbourhood to capture paw prints (see Hacker et al. 2016).

Here, we focus on the next stage, the ‘mapping’ phase, which extended over a three month period and during which two of the participating classes continued to ethnographically explore the environments near their schools in terms of human-rat cohabitation. The young people were recruited by their teacher and they belonged to two different school classes. We did not specifically collect background data on their demographics, but during the research we noticed that the backgrounds of the young people (15 students altogether) were diverse, however, they represented an otherwise exclusive group in that they all had been accepted to a curricular program with an emphasis on natural sciences. The combination of the researchers’ backgrounds in multispecies educational ethnography (Hohti and Tammi 2019; Rautio, Tammi, and Hohti 2021); the study on urban marginalisation (Tuominen 2020; 2022); urban rat research (Aivelo and Nygren 2020; Kervinen et al. 2024); and animal sociology (Simonen 2023) fuelled diverse perspectives and questions in the research: *How do we share our urban environment with rats? What does it mean that our environment is multispecies and how do we become attentive to multispecies co-habitation? What kinds of relations do we recognise, discover, and co-create when moving from one species to a broader multispecies community?* Because multispecies methodologies are only emerging, the topical questions were intertwined with methodological ones: *What does a research approach based on multispecies ethnographic walks enable and what remains beyond its scope? What kinds of cross-generational and multispecies ways of knowing might emerge during the ethnographic process?*

One of the participating schools was located in Bear Hill, an area known as a ‘problem area’, one that is publicly often discussed as an example of ‘failed’ urbanity and immigration, at times even regarded as a symbol of these. This prompted us to delve deeper into the specificities of stigmatisation and gaining a reputation, and to examine these as parts of the more-than-human city.

The five research sessions started with a meeting aimed at refreshing participants’ experiences from the ‘tracing’ phase in preparation for the ethnographic walks conducted in small groups. We challenged young people to think beyond only positive and unproblematic encounters with nonhuman animals. By bringing up ‘unloved others’ (Rose and van Dooren 2011), that is, vilified urban animals such as rats, we aimed to make space for an understanding that the difficulties of sustainable co-living do not lie somewhere outside young people’s innocent worlds, awaiting solutions from them in the future, but that such issues are part of their everyday lives in the here and now. This aim does not sit harmoniously in the dominant pedagogies, which usually emphasise positive connections with nature and sideline the possible tensions and conflicts within the urban environments that the young people live in (see also Hohti and MacLure 2022). It is also much more common for the school institution to accommodate a natural scientific research paradigm with its clear subject–object positions than more relational notions, such as place-making and cohabitation. At the beginning of the mapping phase of the research project, we spent some time talking to the students about these challenges, trying to explicitly shift to a more open-ended ‘gatherings of questions and kinds’ (Van Dooren, Kirksey, and Münster 2016) and to avoid a mere species observation paradigm.

Our ethnographic walks were guided by open-endedness and experimentation (see Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006) around the loose task of attending to rats’ presence in the neighbourhood. This open-endedness proved vital, because it allowed conversations to flow and invited experiences

from the previous, 'tracing' phase as well as personal memories and local narratives. The walks, altogether five, were typically 45 minutes long, and they were framed by a starting session and an end discussion in the class. Two of the walks were accompanied by researchers, while the rest of them were conducted by the young people in groups of 4–6. During the research, we coined further improvised questions around urban cohabitation and belonging, such as 'what do you think should be changed in this suburb?' The produced materials include photographs, video materials produced using GoPro cameras and the students' and researchers' own mobile phone cameras, written fieldnotes as well as photos, videos, and text messages shared in the project WhatsApp group, and media texts of various kinds. These were all produced in a mundane and low threshold way, the primary emphasis being on paying attention, allowing stories and memories to flow, and thinking and talking whilst walking. All the empirical work was conducted in Finnish, and the vignettes included in this article have been translated into English by the authors.

The analysis of the empirical materials was guided by multispecies narrative and ethnographic approaches (Hohti and Tammi 2024; Ogden, Hall, and Tanita 2013), and conceptual and theoretical thinking drawn from the above presented literature. Watching the visual materials side by side with the textual field notes, we paid attention to assemblages that seemed to involve particularly interesting 'questions and kinds' (Van Dooren, Kirksey, and Münster 2016) in relation to our research questions. These assemblages were selected to undergo a more detailed analytical discussion, which proceeded through the movements of at times *narrowing down* the focus with the research questions, and again *broadening* the scope with each of the researcher–authors introducing concepts and viewpoints based on their respective areas of expertise. In this way, the analysis has also taken an experimental characteristic, whereby empirical experiences and theoretical ideas have pushed each other to new directions.

'Rat multiple' in the city and in society

Before engaging with the empirical analytical chapters, let us briefly pay attention to the specific species we followed throughout the research project, the brown rat (*Rattus norvegicus*). These animals have shared urban and other environments with humans for as long as we can look back into the history of humankind, although this co-habitation has not been without its tensions for either species (Puckett, Orton, and Munsu-South 2020). One dimension within this conflicting history is that rats have been the target of large-scale violence when used as test animals in laboratories. Because of this, we actually know more about rat bodies and their functions than about our own (Aivelo and Nygren 2020). Our knowledge of human physiology then is largely based on the knowledge we have about rats' bodies, and rats' genetic heritage serves as the foundation for our entire knowledge of genetics (Birke 2003). Whereas in the laboratory rats' value depends on the way their bodies can be used as sources of scientific knowledge, especially in substituting for the human body in medical experiments, in homes pet rats are well-loved and considered intelligent and fun as companions. These more positive attitudes certainly prevailed among the young participants of this study, many of whom were engaged caretakers for animals and some of whom also had pet rats at home. The negative connotations were mostly connected to societal attitudes rather than their own personal views. In all, the entire research project can be seen as contributing to an increased sensitivity towards rats' lives and agency in the city, but importantly, combined with an awareness of the sometimes irresolvable complexities concerning multispecies co-living.

Historically, urban rats have symbolised dirt, vectors of disease, and they have represented darkness, poverty, and crime (Cole 2016). Rat–human relations carry intense mixtures of emotions, which vary according to place and location (Aivelo and Nygren 2020). These aspects were taken up by a group of young people in conversation with one of the researchers:

[Researcher:] Why don't humans like rats?¹

Because they bring diseases.

Because they are impure animals that eat garbage, spread diseases.

They eat houses, and eat food like they also eat the structures of the house.

Like they gnaw on wood.

But I have always been taught that all living creatures have their purpose in this world.

„

[Researcher:] What do others think?

Same.

True, like there is also a purpose as to why we are here.

Right, to destroy the world.

In contrast to rats in laboratories or homes, wild rats and their ecologies have received surprisingly little attention, with numerous questions about them remaining completely unanswered. The hard to estimate number of urban rats in their underground habitats, their hard to control movements, and the fast reproduction cycle of this species are examples of biological understandings that cast rats as problematic. For some, these kinds of understandings have been taken up in discourses of racialisation and othering in relation to marginalised human groups or phenomena that can become politically labelled as ‘uncontrolled’ such as immigration (Sarasohn 2021).

How might ‘rat multiple’ (de Bondt, Mandy de Wilde, and Jaffe 2023), both known and unknown, both ubiquitous and rarely seen in their habitats, inform us about ‘nature’ in urban environments, and what perspectives might thinking with rats open up with regard to societies, cities, and young people? If we think of place-making as a lively, complex, and messy process (Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006), with rats, this process can be explored from a specific vantage point. Specific material flows and alliances become actualised in connection with rats’ habits, bodily needs, and capacities, and their connections to flows of nutrients and waste materials (de Bondt, Mandy de Wilde, and Jaffe 2023). Recent discussions within children’s geographies also have focused on troubling animal relations and hidden-in-plain-sight processual materials such as percolating wastewater, stating that these can generate new understanding of how environments and societal processes such as class, racism, and colonial histories co-exist (Horton and Krafl 2018). Thinking with urban rats, their fleeting presence, and their affective becomings in the city, we want similarly to broaden the notions of citizenship and urban ecologies. We seek to illuminate urban belonging beyond the perspective of benefits of animal companionship for humans, and to reconceptualise urban ecologies beyond the carefully planned and controlled portions of ‘nature’ such as parks that are invited in cities for the purposes of human well-being, recreation and learning.

Might this be a rat’s hole? Beyond visibility

We will now take a closer look at selected moments during our empirical work. During the ethnographic walks, one of the young participants typically held and directed a GoPro camera. Watching the video footage in retrospect, we find a lively unfolding of a ‘world in movement’ (Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006), in which feelings, atmospheres and questions are generated along with the physical rhythms of walking, slowing down, and again speeding up. The walks typically proceeded from the school towards the nearby open-air shopping mall and finally in and across this commercial and community space. In the previous tracking phase, there were numerous rat tracks on the track plates set in and around the mall, suggesting substantial rat presence. The mall dating from the 1970s, its facades of the houses and the shop windows, an alcohol store, food stores and cafes, an abandoned playground, all are in a state of relative neglect. The choice of global regional

food served in the restaurants reflects the ethnic diversity of the inhabitants' backgrounds, roughly one third of which are immigrant (Tuominen 2022).

An abandoned playground in the middle of an open-air shopping centre

That's where the rats were.

Right in the middle

Someone remembers having seen rats.

[Researcher] talks about a 'rat lady' who was known for feeding rats in Bear Hill.

Now, the playground equipment has been left to deteriorate,

rocking horses have lost their heads and bodies.

Only the structure remains.

A sad sight to see.

Ghosts of children, ghosts of rats.

[Researcher 1] asks if anyone has ever seen children play on this playground

A (one of the young people) has.

B (another student) dramatises:

Let's go quickly if we want to survive!

Camera pans out:

The pavement of the shopping centre, a grocery store, a halal store ...

'Feeding the birds is prohibited'.

(fieldnotes)

Bear Hill carries a notorious reputation since its construction in the 1960s, enhanced by media stories focusing on problems such as poverty or the surge in the number of rats in the area. Tuominen (2020) explains that, at different moments, these kinds of suburban estates on the margins of Helsinki, Finland, have been connected to issues such as rootlessness, segregation, intergenerational poverty, and the unsuccessful integration of immigrants as well as a sense of peripherality in relation to the city centre. As for our research site, the district is in fact connected to the urban sphere of the capital city through an open-air shopping centre and the extension of the metro line. Statistics also do not support its association with poverty more generally. However, the stickiness of stigmatisation means that its reputation persists even if not fully substantiated by factual data.

Place-making centres *becomings* rather than steady beings, allowing us to acknowledge that visible beings in the present are only temporary stabilisations. Here, the openness and ambivalence of stigmatisation, discussed by Tuominen (2022) and Peltola and colleagues (2023), became visible when we juxtaposed material observations with sometimes conflicting stories that stretched across multiple places and times. For instance, even if the mall playground was now in a sad and neglected state, later in class one student talked about it with a sense of nostalgia and affection, arguing against ongoing plans to demolish the old mall and to replace it with a new one: 'Imagine if your own childhood place was torn down just like that!'

Experimental multispecies ethnographic walks allowed us to engage with *ad hoc* themes and playful engagements. But the relatively open-ended approach also fuelled insecurities among both students and researchers: after beginning the ethnographic walks, it soon became clear that rats were hard to find. In fact, there were no rats around at all for us to observe.

We are staring at a hole in the ground.

Someone shares a story of a rat that attacked someone nearby.

[Researcher] remembers that, during his study, there was an old lady who was known to feed rats.

Is this really a rat hole?

Or is it a rabbit hole?

We notice an opening under the door of a garbage collection point.

It was here.

Someone once saw a rat right here.

(fieldnotes)

Rats as primarily nocturnal animals rarely venture out during the daytime. Urban rats spend their lives burrowing in the soil and moving in a city's underground structures, which makes them close to impossible to reach. Instead of liking adventures in new places, rats avoid humans and are cautious and quick to learn from threatening situations. This means that they do not easily step in traps, and once a rat has been trapped, other rat individuals learn to avoid traps. In all, the reasons behind the difficulties of trapping rats are also behind the little amount of research on wild rats.

Along with our growing uncertainty about the possibility of examining rats as our co-habitants in the city as we intended, we began asking: *Are we trying to attend to something that cannot be attended to?* Our research group shared their doubts during various conversations. Even if multi-species co-existence is a basic fact of life – something we discussed with the young people at the beginning of the mapping exercises – the video footage of an empty concrete yard behind the shopping mall revealed little of this. How could we develop multispecies attentiveness in a seemingly monospecies environment, such as the mall, which had signs reading 'do not feed the birds' and 'do not bring dogs to the mall'? During our walks, we noticed spikes on fences which made it impossible for pigeons to land.² We discussed the signs telling us not to feed the birds even if it is commonly known that the real problem is the rats that benefit from the bird feeding practice. However, the figure of a rat is seldom added to such signs – because it reinforces stigma, we speculated.

Perhaps the methodological insecurities we felt can be seen as necessary *hesitation* when moving towards the limitations of human-centric inquiries. A phase of hesitation might be needed to open up space for something new, for example, unlearning mastery in more-than-human methodology (Weaver and Snaza 2017) or experiments conducted 'inexpertly', (Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006). According to Hinchliffe and Whatmore (2006), an inexpert approach is required to examine fields of becoming which are neither ready nor stable and which unsettle simple ideas of presence and time. While informed through experience and observation, inexpert experiments are likely to throw up surprises and generate new configurations. This kind of a stance also allows us to make space for other than human questions, explanations, conditions, and modalities – for others to 'participate in the invention' (Despret 2016; Stengers 2000, 160, cited in Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006).

In the absence of physical rats that we could have observed in the neighbourhood, narrative and memory traces began to gain significance. Stories about rats, such as in the above field notes example, added one dimension to the seemingly human-only urban place in the present moment. Van Dooren and Rose (2012) argue that multispecies stories and meanings are not just layered upon a pre-existing landscape, but that they both emerge from and impact upon the way in which places come to be. Similarly, Spruce (2020) examines LGBTQ place-making using situated memory as a lens to understand how minoritised narratives about the past play a role in the urban politics of

the present. In some cases, the stories we heard were personal memories – ‘someone once saw a rat right here, behind this garbage collection point’. Some of the narratives became connected to the neighbourhood through media, including news about unwanted urban phenomena, frequently situated where we conducted our research. One such storyline stems from a 1980s movie, “Täältä tullaan elämä [Life, here we come]”, situated in the mall, depicting the hopeless perspectives of ‘problem youth’ in the suburb. Engaging narrative place-making means that we can think of multi-species cohabitation as a phenomenon that disrupts commonplace politics that relies on presence and agentic individuals (humans, rats) acting against the stable physical background of a place (the mall backyard). Both media and other stories participate in the making of a particular kind of urban ecology. As sticky stories of stigmatisation, they render unwanted phenomena as more present than suggested by their sheer material presence.

Waste–Human–Rat–Waste

[student, acting as if a nature documentary narrator in the video:]

Where do we find rats?

In places with food and humans.

Where do we find food and humans?

In Bear Hill (the neighbourhood).

Where does one put the food when humans are not keeping an eye on it?

In bins.

(video camera films down the road toward the mall and zooms in on corners to find garbage bins and trash)

Following our attempts to find traces of actual rats (which, ultimately, we did not), we moved on to look for ‘ratty’ atmospheres (Kervinen et al. 2024). The above videotaped conversation demonstrates how garbage, dirt, and waste became actualised as potentially ratty, vibrant materials (Bennett 2010). If rats are multiple (de Bondt, Mandy de Wilde, and Jaffe 2023), so is waste – that is, the anonymous stuff ‘falling between valued objects and simple dust’ (Kennedy 2007, 7). What we call trash depends on its use value – or, rather, lack thereof – for human purposes. Recent feminist waste studies point out that waste is a lively category that creates a fleeting ontology of its own. Fleetingness means that waste adheres to a temporality that exceeds human time and relationality. The category of waste is multiple in that anything and everything can become waste, and things can simultaneously be and not be waste depending on the perspective and the perceiver (Clark and Yusoff 2017; Yusoff and Hird 2016). As such, no entity is in essence waste, while all entities have the potential to *become* waste at a different time and place.

A garbage bin again

a student sticks his head in it, no rats there

The camera zooms in to the inside of the bin.

A beer can

Oh damn what turds

We walk to the shopping centre

Those must have been left behind by an adult man.

[Researcher:] Are you serious?

Yeah, why, this is Bear Hill.

What do you mean this is Bear Hill?

Well, this just happens to be a place where people randomly poop around, business as usual.

(video transcript)

Rummaging through garbage is likely to reveal intimate details related to personal hygiene, private thoughts, political affiliations, or finances (Spelman 2011). In this perspective, trash provides a resource for understanding what individuals and communities are actually about: ‘We know ourselves through waste’ (Spelman 2011, 323–324). In a similar way, Aivelo and Nygren (2020) claim that rats, when making use of what is left behind by humans, reveal unpleasant facts about our societies, namely, our unsustainable consumption habits, and the ruptures and overflows within seemingly controlled human societies.

Another garbage bin.

I can’t see rats’, says [a student], who sticks the camera inside the bin.

A Covid mask, a cigarette box, a disposable coffee cup, a dog poo bag?

(video transcript)

Humans, rats, food, and waste are tied to each other: they form a network, or rather, meshwork (Barua 2023), which involves flows of nutrients such as fats and carbohydrates across bodies and as actors in the relational formation of a city. The urban human–rat–waste–human connections, their ‘lumped-togetherness’ (Horton and Kraftl 2018), means that human flourishing is inherently tied to rat flourishing, and the complete eradication of rats from the immediate vicinity of human habitats becomes impossible (de Bondt, Mandy de Wilde, and Jaffe 2023). A recent example took place during Covid-19, when rats left city centres together with humans to live in the suburbs where the flow of nutrients were relocated (Parsons et al. 2021). Like rats, waste is also impossible to completely eradicate. To live is to produce waste, and to live in an urban suburb is to share some of this waste with rats in an intimate and affective connectedness (Aivelo and Nygren 2020).

‘Now!’ We are approaching the mall

It smells like food or some kind of grease here.

(video transcript)

In the suburb we studied, a fast food restaurant served as an important if not magnetic place for young people, from which smells extended far, carrying the promise of tasty grease and carbohydrates. The waste–food–rat emerged as a sensory observation, an atmosphere of smelly messages that would potentially open up some specificities related to the human and rat inhabitants in the area. By definition, junk food is close to waste. It is cost-effective and heavily marketed to families with children, and in this neighbourhood, it also is one of the viable options families have in terms of eating out. Furthermore, hamburgers are often the first meals young people can afford to buy themselves when they occasionally have an extra euro or two. Parenting that favours junk food is not only considered a marker of poverty, but also a sign of a loss of control in life more broadly (Carpenter and Savage 2021).

While evidence exists for the various health problems caused by junk food in children (e.g. Bhaskar and Ola 2012), our analytical conversations went on to explore the effects cheap fats and the salty and sugary leftovers from fast food meals might have on the other-than-human animals around. All the inhabitants of the suburb (human or other-than-human) have the basic need to survive, and through sharing nutrients such as fats and carbohydrates, at different points of the life cycle of junk food products, they relate to the same economy (Aivelo and Nygren 2020). The junk food–waste–rat–child entanglement offers us one specific viewpoint into place-making, highlighting the complexities of conviviality (Duhn 2017). When zooming in into the detail of this complexity, we can analyse human cultures and industries as not so human only. In this example, the multinational junk food companies’ aggressive marketing strategies secure them a stable position in the everyday worlds of human children, but also in the worlds of rats. As Hinchliffe and Whatmore (2006) stated, urban ecologies are urban in ways that go beyond simple sets of obstacles or

opportunities. Urban inhabitants of a city are genuinely more-than-human, more-than-animal, and more-than-plant. They are complex entanglements, not clear-cut matters of facts but rather 'matters of controversy' mutually affecting and affected by their fields of becoming (Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006).

This place cannot be tidied up!

One reason for our interest in multifaceted stigmatisation was the fact that even if the research was focused on a multispecies city, the conversations with young people frequently turned to specific aesthetic aspects of the environment. The following conversation took place in the classroom as the actual research session was ending. Two students remained seated at their desks and began debating how to make the suburb a nicer place. The atmosphere was heated.

Tidying tidying ...

... well if they tidy this place up, after two days it looks exactly the same

Well then there will simply be more tidying

Can they afford it?

Well then just add more garbage bins

But they will never put trash in the bin anyway

Well you tell me what should be done!

I don't know. I just told you

[some talk about moving away]

Why do we f***** stay here then?

No-one is f***** interested in how it looks here

You can buy things in the store and that's good ... there is not so much to change here

[one of the students carries the remains of a crab (the previous lesson was on the anatomy and dissection of crabs)]

Another shouts, 'I told you I don't want that crab'

It smells like shit here anyway

[They talk about ways to keep the mall clean. Perhaps build a glass ceiling ... Add more cleaners]

Do you think people would care

Not all the drunk men are drunk all the time

The mall should be demolished and built anew

(video transcript)

In his study on spatial stigmatisation, Tuominen (2022) highlights that in the reputedly disadvantaged areas around Helsinki, districts seen as poor 'problem areas' in fact resemble a fragmented mosaic of poverty, with only small pockets plagued with social problems. The 'deep narrative' (Tuominen 2022) overarching the whole area can still be a stigmatised one. This narrative is supported by atmospheric elements such as a stickiness, ambivalence, fleetingness, and the sentiments of unpleasant secrets and a persistent untidiness or an unwanted intimacy. Thus, spatial stigma not only operates as attitudes, but also as an atmosphere (Stewart 2011), an entanglement of materials,

affects, and bodies. The ambivalences of this atmosphere are reflected in the conversation above, in which dirt and solutions (or the lack thereof) to removing it entangle with a hopeless perspective related to the place and the people in the neighbourhood.

An aesthetic and affective urban history connects rats to young people in particular: the wish to control young people in urban spaces is not unlike the wish to control rat populations in cities. Just as rats, young people are also often viewed as occupying the wrong place at the wrong time when in public. Urban spaces are seldom only for ‘being’ (Goffman 1963) – for the type of dwelling that young people tend to do, dwelling that does not go well together with the demands of consumer citizenship. When young people make use of public places, they often cross the borders of the useful and healthy (educational) spaces built for them. Young people are viewed as out of control and suspicious when loitering in streets and malls without a specific agenda (Pyyry 2016).

The closeness of children to the vilified urban animals have their historical roots. Laakkonen (2011) documented the urban environmental history of Finnish children, drawing upon the memory and narrative sources from the beginning of the 1900s. In those days, children engaged in a variety of games and play in polluted environments, rich with the potential offered by both trash objects, dirt, and other-than-human animals. Both waste and rats occupied a central role in these childhood worlds: rats were everywhere, and children could, for example, earn money both by killing rats and by collecting waste (Laakkonen 2011).

Recent childhood studies have paid attention to the assumptions of purity and authenticity associated with childhoods, which can limit the ways in which we acknowledge and understand those childhoods lived outside the spheres of white, Western, protected childhood (Breslow 2021). These kinds of limitations also apply to commonplace environmental education practices that lean on authentic and unspoiled imageries of nature when enhancing connectedness to nature (Mcphie and Clarke 2020) and to the limits set to young people in urban spaces in the name of safety, healthy development and consumerist citizenship. Even if children have a historically close relationship with complex urbanised and industrialised environments, young people dwelling in and with public spaces is seldom viewed as meaningful and as learning (for exception see Pyyry 2016). Children’s awkward and ambivalent experiences with polluted waters, shit, or vilified animals such as urban seagulls or rats have only recently been taken seriously as environmental relationships that matter and as deserving of theorising (Horton and Kraftl 2018; Authors).

[Researcher:] Where should we take the rats if they are not accepted here?

[Student 1:] We should take them in the woods.

[Student 2:] They wouldn’t be able to make it there.

(video transcript)

Akin to stating that trash belongs to Bear Hill despite efforts to try to tidy it up, the students talk here about rats as inherently belonging to the city: rats are urban cohabitants and the city is their home.

Conclusions: attentiveness and hesitance

More-than-human everyday urbanism is still a somewhat emerging focus of research, as the city continues to be understood as a predominantly human space constructed in dualistic opposition to wild and unspoiled ‘nature’ (Schuurman 2024; Van Patter 2023), or as an arena built for humans in which other than humans enter as ‘animated constructs’ or as transgressive forces that unsettle metropolitan order (Barua 2023, 4). In this multidisciplinary research, we have attended to other-than-human beings’ roles in the constitution of cities and developed ways of including them in the theorisation of urbanity and spatial stigmatisation. The multispecies ethnographic walks highlighted stigmatisation as a sticky process that folds in bodies, places, stories, histories, as well as

materials such as waste. The natural scientific perspectives on rats' bodily capacities and rat populations' movements in the city enriched the ways in which we could ethnographically examine the city. The ambivalence that we transported from the anthropological perspectives on stigmatisation to the study of multispecies urbanity served as a methodological force that gestured us to the city as a lively, open meshwork (Barua 2023). The collective cultivation of 'arts of attentiveness' (Van Dooren, Kirksey, and Münster 2016) involving young people as local experts entailed developing sensitivities towards a range of sensory, affective, and narrative traces such as personal memories, rumours, and media stories, as well as the 'lumped-together' (Horton and Kraftl 2018) human-rat-waste-human connections. Historically formed connections between young people and rats took us to approach questions of control and belonging beyond useful, economic citizenship. Together, all these perspectives allowed for an examination of spatial stigmatisation as a phenomenon that emerged with the formation of the city, intertwined with multispecies place-making.

Our study offers openings towards nuanced articulations of urban cohabitation. We argue that the work done at the intersections of societal inequalities and marginalisation on the one hand, and multispecies urban place-making on the other, requires holding space for constant movement across the empirical, conceptual and methodological dimensions of each of the disciplines involved, allowing creative impulses and interconnections. In closing, however, we wish to take further some important cautions resulting from methodological insecurities that emerged during our study.

In our study, there were moments in which we felt a particularly clear necessity of halting and thinking twice. These hesitations emerged especially in connection with three empirical challenges. The first one relates to the topic of stigma itself. Even if stigmatisation was not initially the focus of the research project, along with starting to theorise this phenomenon, we found ourselves entering the risky terrains that researchers of stigmatisation have earlier brought up: possibly reinforcing stigma through doing research on stigma (see Peltola et al. 2023). This suggests a particular need for nuance and care when conducting research on marginalisation, also across species divides. The second hesitation emerged in connection with our attempts to attend to the fleeting presence of rats in the city. This prompted us to broaden our methodological repertoire to encompass not only physical but also sensory, narrative and memory traces of rats, which all became understood as contributing to urban place-making. This points at the need for frequently revising any assumptions concerning straightforward visibility, presence and time, when conducting multispecies ethnography (see Hinchliffe and Whatmore 2006).

The last hesitation concerns the notion of arts of attentiveness in multispecies research. Even if our multispecies ethnography enabled glimpses of other than human cohabitants of the city not simply as nice additions to urbanity, or as external agents that intervene in human environments, much remains unexplored in terms of nonhuman sensing and activity, most of which happens outside human sensory and knowledge systems (Lorimer, Hodgetts, and Barua 2019). For van Dooren and colleagues (2016), arts of attentiveness are about learning to notice more, but also about learning how to better respond to one another. The more we know about rats' participation and agency in the making of our cities, including *their* ways of noticing, the more we might value them and the multispecies ecologies of our cities. Yet, this is never certain, given that other kinds of responses are also possible. Rousell (2023) discusses these darker possibilities pointing out how becoming responsive to interconnections and dependency relations across species also entails 'learning to embrace the tentacular darkness of Earthly forces that lurk underneath our all-too-human experiences of the world' (13). The more we research stigmatisation, the more we risk increasing stigma. The more we want to know, the more we also intervene, and the ethics of this intervention must be constantly considered when making methodological decisions. We know that it is fully possible and fully commonplace to do passionate research on animals from a human-centric perspective, even in cases where the stated agenda is more-than-human (see Pedersen and Pini 2017). Thus, even a multispecies research project can risk becoming caught in a loop of anthropocentrism and instrumentalism by, for example, emphasising human sensory capacities or granting value to other-than-humans based on their usefulness.

In the context of anthropocentric and monospecies legacies strongly shaping both city planning, education, and qualitative research methodology, developing sustainable urban politics *for all* requires collaborative conceptual and empirical work that extends across social and natural sciences and remains open to experimentation to some extent. In this article, we have engaged in such work, rethinking marginalisation and stigmatisation as multispecies processes that *make* urban place. To conclude, we want to highlight ethics of hesitance as a necessary addition to the arts of attentiveness towards multispecies worlds. The above discussed suspicions and insecurities could be viewed as cultivation of strategic hesitance (Despret 2018) reminding us about the fact that the processes of urban becoming and attending to these are partial and non-innocent.

Notes

1. The vignettes presented in italics are excerpts from the researchers' fieldnotes and videotaped and audiotaped conversations. All names used in this manuscript are pseudonyms, and some other minor details have been changed to preserve anonymity.
2. In urban ecologies, what limits some may invite others to innovate. Crows and magpies have reportedly utilised the metal spikes meant to deter them for building nests (Hiemstra et al. 2023).

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